

Gas as surfactant in three-phase systems from methane, *p*-xylene and water: neutron imaging and molecular dynamics simulations

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ABSTRACT

Pressurized gases act as surfactants as they adsorb on the gas–liquid interfaces, and thus reduce the surface tension. We use neutron imaging (NI) and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations to study if the dissolved gas retains the surfactancy for adsorption on the liquid-liquid interfaces. NI was used to observe the shapes of the mobile interfaces in wide-bore metal tubes containing pressurized methane (CH₄), perdeuterated *p*-xylene (*p*-C₈D₁₀), and water (10.88 mol.% of H₂O in D₂O) at temperatures between 7.0 and 30.0 °C. The analysis of time-series radiograms of the system exposed to methane pressure steps up to 101 bar enabled us to derive the interfacial tensions (*l-g* and *l-l*), methane diffusivity, solubility, and partial molar volume in the *p*-xylene rich phase. So determined interfacial tensions had the experimental uncertainties of 2 mN·m⁻¹ and 16 mN·m⁻¹ for the *g-l* and *l-l* interfaces, respectively. The uncertainty increases with decreasing density difference at the interface and increasing surface tension. We thus calibrated MD calculations to the available experimental data from NI and from the literature, and predicted the properties of the three-phase systems from methane, *p*-xylene, and water. The interfacial tension for the *l-l* interface did not change with methane pressure (± 1 mN/m, no surfactancy up to 100 bar), while the interface structure was sensitive to the parameterization of the electrostatic charge distribution within the *p*-xylene molecule. The surface affinity of methane to the *p*-xylene-water interface is only minor and changes from positive excess for uncharged *p*-xylene (united-atom Trappe force-field) to negative depletion for *p*-xylene with distributed partial charges.

INTRODUCTION

The stability of oil-water interfaces is known to be greatly influenced by the presence of charged species (e.g. ion-specific effects) and by the presence of dissolved gases. With focus on the latter, the stability of emulsions containing dissolved gas (chiefly air) at atmospheric pressure is lower than that of the degassed ones. Bridging of the oil droplets through coalesced gas microbubbles is one of the likely key mechanisms [1-12]. Stability of oil-water emulsions is clearly related to the wastewater treatments – water containing dissolved and dispersed hydrocarbons is the main waste stream produced the oil and gas industry [13-17]. Besides the systems containing low concentrations of dissolved gases at pressures near atmospheric, the water-oil emulsions saturated by gases (e.g. methane) at high pressures (e.g. 100 bar) occur at oil well conditions [16]. While the microbubble coalescence expectably occurs also at high gas pressures, adsorption at phase interfaces is inevitably of increased importance than at atmospheric pressure. We aim to contribute knowledge of molecular interactions at oil-water interfaces in the presence of dissolved gas at elevated pressures, and gas-water and gas-oil interfaces.

Pressurized gases can act as surfactants at gas-liquid interfaces, which was observed for systems such as methane/water [18-20] and methane/*p*-xylene [21]. This surfactancy results from van der Waals interactions [1], and is associated with the positive adsorption of the gas on the interface leading to the decrease of surface tension. Interestingly, surface excess of methane at the methane/water interface reaches maximum at about 100 bar, but decreases at higher pressures and becomes negligible or even negative above 500 bar (0-50 °C). This nontrivial behavior is consistent with Gibbs interpretation of the plateau in surface tension observed experimentally near 500 bar of methane [19].

In this work, we study whether the dissolved methane acts as a surfactant at the liquid-liquid interface in bulk three-phase systems from methane, *p*-xylene, and water. The latter two compounds serve as model components of crude oil and condensable impurities in natural gas being the severe freeze-out formers [22, 23]. To this aim, we combine neutron imaging (NI) with molecular dynamics (MD) simulations [21]. NI enabled the observation of the shapes of the macroscopic phase interfaces in the three-phase system at high pressure [24], assessment of swelling and concentration over time upon pressurization. This provided observables (see below) for the MD calibration followed by predictions and molecular-scale analysis of the water/*p*-xylene interface in the presence of dissolved methane.

THEORY AND METHODS

Neutron imaging

NI experiments were performed using the previously reported one-pot method [21, 25]. Cylindrical cell parallel to gravity containing the three-phase system was imaged using the NEUTRA beamline [26] at Paul Scherrer Institute. MIDI-box detector system using a 30 μm -thick $\text{Gd}_2\text{O}_3\text{:Tb}$ scintillator screen and an sCMOS camera (Andor Neo) fitted with a 100-mm objective (Zeiss Makro-Planar) were used

images of 2560 (W) x 2160 (H) pixels in size were collected with an isotropic pixel pitch of 20.3 μm , the spatial resolution is estimated to be better than 80 micrometers. Two cells (titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V, inner diameter 9.0 ± 0.1 mm) were imaged simultaneously. One contained methane (CH_4), water (10.88 mol.% of H_2O in D_2O), and *p*-xylene ($p\text{-C}_8\text{D}_{10}$), which is the focus of the current work. The other cell contained methane (CH_4) and *p*-xylene ($p\text{-C}_8\text{D}_{10}$), results were reported elsewhere [25]. Isotopically labeled compounds were used because of the significant difference in neutron cross-sections of protium (H) and deuterium (D) [27]. Chemicals and gases are listed in Table 1. We used this difference to adjust contrast among the phases in the studied system and to quantify the dissolved methane in the *p*-xylene phase (see below). Experiments were initiated by the steep change of methane pressure in the cells from atmospheric to a preset value. Liquid perdeuterated *p*-xylene ($p\text{-C}_8\text{D}_{10}$) was layered over water (10.88 \pm 0.05 mol.% of H_2O in D_2O) in a perpendicular cylindrical cell [21, 25] maintained at a constant temperature, and exposed to a methane (CH_4) pressure step at the zero time. The onion-peeling algorithm [28] was used to provide the tomographic reconstructions at the central plane of the sample. Further details on the experiment and processing of the radiographies were described earlier [21, 25].

Table 1. Used gases and chemicals, initial purity is as in the certificate of analysis by the supplier.

chemical	supplier, initial purity, CAS number
methane (CH_4)	PanGas, 4.5, CAS 74-82-8
nitrogen (N_2)	Messer, 4.0, CAS 7727-37-9
<i>p</i> -xylene ($p\text{-C}_8\text{D}_{10}$)	Armar, 99.59 atom-% D
water (H_2O)	18.2 M Ω cm at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$, Millipore ZRQS0P300, CAS 7732-18-5
water (D_2O)	Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, 99,93 atom-% D, CAS 7789-20-0
acetone	Penta, > 99.9 wt.% (rinsing agent), CAS 67-64-1

Menisci in perpendicular tube

The shapes of mobile, axially symmetric interfaces under gravity can be parameterized using the Young-Laplace equation [24, 29-31]

$$z = \frac{\gamma}{\Delta \rho g} \left(\frac{z'''}{(1+z'^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{z'}{r(1+z'^2)^{1/2}} \right) \quad (1)$$

In this notation, the distance from the tube axis ranges from zero to the tube inner radius, $r \in (0, R)$. The meniscus shape $z(r) - z(0)$ at the central plane is obtained by numerically solving the boundary value problem $z'(r=0) = 0$; $z'(r=R) = \cot(\theta)$. Parameters are contact angle at the inner tube wall (θ), density

difference at the interface ($\Delta\rho$), interfacial tension (γ , IFT, also surface tension), and gravity in Villigen [32] $g = 9.80740 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$. The solution is shown in Fig. 1 for chosen sets of parameters. For $\gamma / (R^2 \Delta\rho) \rightarrow \infty$, converge of the numerically calculated $z(r) - z(0)$ to a circle part satisfying the boundary value problem conditions is observed. This matches the well-known observation that air/water menisci in narrow capillaries in gravity practically have the shape of sphere part [29]. At this limit, gravity does not influence the interface shape, which means loss of sensitivity of the surface tension calculation by fitting Eq. (1); see [24] for details. At the studied conditions, $\gamma/\Delta\rho$ is higher for the water/*p*-xylene than for the methane/*p*-xylene interface, which leads to higher uncertainty of the surface tension of the former. In this work, numerical solutions of Eq. (1) for fixed tube radius were calculated using the midrich routine in Maple software package, γ and θ were optimized using the Gauss-Newton method [33, 34] to fit the interface shape observed using NI. Random uncertainties (cover factor 2) were estimated using the Bonferroni method [33], $\Delta\rho$ was calculated using the equations of state for the pure components [35-37], while the methane concentration distribution and partial molar volume in the *p*-xylene phase was derived from the NI (see below).

Figure 1. Solution of Eq. (1) for indicated parameters, which are similar to those for the methane/*p*-xylene (black curve) and *p*-xylene/water (red curve) interfaces at the studied conditions, circle part (dashed, limit for $\gamma / \Delta\rho \rightarrow \infty$) is shown for comparison, contact angle is 10° in all cases. Adapted from [24].

Methane distribution

The neutron attenuation in the binary liquid mixture of A (CH_4) and B (*p*- C_8D_{10}) containing negligible concentration of water (see below) is described by the Beer-Lambert law in the following the form:

$$\ln \frac{I^0}{I} = \sigma_A N_0 c_A d + \sigma_B N_0 c_B d = \Sigma_A d + \Sigma_B d \quad (2)$$

in which I^0 and I are the incident and transmitted intensities beam intensities, respectively, c_i are molar concentrations, the linear attenuation coefficients of the components (Σ_i) contribute the overall linear attenuation coefficient (Σ). Constants are path length (d) and Avogadro number (N_0). The neutron attenuation in the other two phases is contributed by one component only: *p*-xylene negligibly evaporates into the methane phase [38, 39], and the mutual miscibilities of water (C) and *p*-xylene are low [17, 40] at the studied conditions. The cross-sections (σ) of the components were derived from the tomographic reconstruction of the single-component phases, yielding 189 ± 9 barn for CH₄, 101 ± 3 barn for *p*-C₈D₁₀, and 24.8 ± 0.5 barn for 10.88 mol.% H₂O in D₂O. The molar concentration (c) and density (ρ) of pure methane were calculated using the Peng-Robinson equation of state [35] with parameters ($T_c = 190.564$ K, $p_c = 45.99$ bar, $\omega = 0.0115478$) taken from the database [41]. For the liquids, pure *p*-xylene (*p*-C₈H₁₀) [37] and pure water (H₂O) [36], mole concentrations and densities were calculated from the known equations of state, assuming equal molar volume between the deuterated and protium-based chemicals. Supercooling of *p*-xylene (*p*-C₈D₁₀) was assessed [25] using the available literature data for the melting point of the dry *p*-xylene (*p*-C₈H₁₀) under relevant conditions [22, 42].

The time-dependent swelling of the *p*-xylene phase due to the methane absorption upon the pressurization complicates the application of Eq. (2), mass balance needs to be solved simultaneously. The resulting time- and space-resolved information on volume of the body of revolution and concentration distributions in it. These data were used as input to derive apparent volume, diffusivity in the B-fixed coordinates and apparent Henry's law constant of methane in *p*-xylene using the Fick's second law and the bulk solution thermodynamics as described earlier [21, 25]. To briefly summarize, the Fick's second law was used in its form for the axially-symmetric body in the cylindrical B-fixed (i.e., non-swelling *p*-C₈H₁₀) coordinates [43, 44], thus

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial \tau} = D_A^B \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial \square^2} + D_A^B \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial C}{\partial r} \right) \quad (3)$$

in which C is concentration (mole of A per mole of B), $\xi_z^{low}(r, \tau=0)$, $z^{up}(r, \tau=0)$ is the transformed physical depth coordinate evaluating between the depth coordinates of the upper and lower meniscus coordinate (Fig. 2) at zero time. Eq. (3) was solved numerically using an explicit differentiation scheme [34, 44], initial concentration was set to zero, Dirichlet (constant concentration in the liquid at the interface, $C^{IF} = x_A^{liq}/x_B^{liq}$) and Neumann (impermeable walls and B/C interface) were used. Solution of Eq. (1) was fitted by adjusting D_A^B and C^{IF} (Gauss-Newton, Bonferroni [33, 34]) to the concentration distributions derived from the observed tomographic reconstructions at the central plane of the sample. In this experimentally accessible reference frame, $D_B^B = 0$. The relation [43] of D_A^B diffusivity to those of the compounds A and B in the cell reference frame, which are accessible using MD simulations, is

$$D_A^B = \frac{1}{C^{IF}} \int_0^{C^{IF}} \phi_B^2 [\phi_A (D_B - D_A) + D_A] dC \quad (4)$$

where, ϕ is volume fraction. Apparent Henry's law constant was calculated from C^{IF} and methane pressure, thus

$$H = p_A^{gas/fluid} x_A^{liq} \quad (5)$$

Volume of the liquid (A, B) was calculated as the volume of the body of revolution within the two menisci (Fig. 2), total number of moles $n_{A,t}$ was derived by integrating the respective concentration distributions, $n_{B,t}$ was derived from the volume of the liquid (B) without dissolved gas (A).

$$V = V_A^{app} n_{A,t} + V_B^* n_{B,t} \quad (6)$$

Parameter V_A^{app} stands for the apparent molar volume of A that was calculated by linear regression, V_B^* is the molar volume of pure B at the temperature and pressure of the experiment [37].

Changes of the liquid level (swelling), overall linear attenuation coefficient, and shapes of menisci upon the system pressurization are shown in Fig. 2. As the typical example, the average absolute deviation (AAD) of for the methane/*p*-xylene menisci from Eq. (1) was comparable to the experimental pixel size (20.3 μm), while the AAD for the *p*-xylene/water interface was three to four times that. The reduction of the effective spatial resolution was attributed to high attenuation due to the concave water phase. This, together with the low sensitivity illustrated in Fig. 1, substantially reduced precision of the surface tension evaluation using Eq. (1) in the case of *p*-xylene/water interface.

Figure 2. Onion peeled images of the measuring cell with supercooled perdeuterated *p*-xylene ($p\text{-C}_8\text{D}_{10}$) layered over water (10.88 mol.% of H_2O in D_2O) exposed to methane at 1.0 bar (A) and $100.4 \pm$

0.2 bar (C), both at 7.0 ± 0.2 °C. Fits for the phase interface shapes [red curves, Eq. (1)] are shown in (A, C) and in the plot showing also the detected phase interface and the Average Absolute Deviation for the model and points (B). The inner diameter of the cylindrical cell was $2 \cdot R = 9.0 \pm 0.1$ mm, grayscale corresponds to the linear coefficient of attenuation (A, C). Adapted from [24].

Molecular dynamics

MD simulations were used to model the macroscopic behavior of experimentally investigated three-phase systems: water (C) + *p*-xylene (B) + methane (A). Simulations allow to investigate structural, thermodynamic and transport properties in the bulk solution and at liquid-liquid interface (i.e. *p*-xylene/water) beyond experimental conditions and with atomic resolution. The used MD simulations rely on TIP4P/2005 water model [45] and all-atom parameterization of *p*-xylene from LigParGen based on Lennard-Jones OPLS-AA parameters with 1.14*CM1A or 1.14*CM1A-LBCC partial atomic charges [46-48] with cut-off set to 2.0 nm. The long-range electrostatics was accounted for by particle mesh Ewald (PME) summation with a grid spacing of 0.16 nm in conjunction with tinfoil boundary condition as implemented in GROMACS [49]. This approach was demonstrated to reproduce the phase behavior of neat liquids, presenting a starting point for simulations of mixtures at multi-phase coexistence. All MD simulations were performed in the GROMACS simulation package [50] with a timestep of 2 fs. In all cases, periodic boundary conditions (PBC) in three-dimensional (3D) space were applied. The simulated systems were divided into groups according to the number of co-existing phases.

First set of simulations contained systems of three coexisting phases with an explicit presence of three different interfaces, i.e. the slab simulation setup (Fig. 3a). These simulations mimic the (idealized) experimental design and prove the ability of MD simulations to model multiphase systems. This setup enabled the evaluation of equilibrium density profiles across the interfaces (solubilities). The system for these slab simulations was initially a rectangular cuboid with equilibrium side lengths of ca $4.1 \times 4.1 \times 30$ nm, where the width of water and *p*-xylene phases was ca 6-7 nm, and the remaining space represented methane gas phase. System consisted of 500 *p*-xylene molecules, 4000 water and 300-1500 methane molecules based on previously calculated Henry's law constants (in order to have a stable gas phase of a reasonable size), which were distributed in separated regions at the start of the simulation utilizing the PACKMOL package [51]. After energy minimalization the slab was simulated for 60 ns in isothermal-semi-isobaric N_pT ensemble (compressible in *z*-direction only). The first 30 ns were taken out as an equilibration and last 30 ns were used for analysis. All three-phase simulations were performed with three separate V-rescale thermostats [52] ($\tau_T = 0.5$ ps) used for separate temperature coupling of methane, *p*-xylene, and water and C-rescale barostat ($\tau_p = 2.0$ ps) [53].

Second, we have simulated two-phase (slab) systems. Namely, liquid-liquid interfaces; water/*p*-xylene, liquid-liquid interface (*p*-xylene saturated with methane)/water, shown in Fig. 3b, gas methane interface with liquid water and gas methane interface with liquid *p*-xylene. All these simulations were 40 ns long and were performed in isothermal-semi-isobaric NpT ensemble (compressible in *z*-direction only). The first 20 ns used for equilibration and 20 ns for analysis. The compositions and initial sizes of the systems are in Table 2. All two-phase simulations were performed with separate V-rescale thermostat [52] ($\tau_T = 0.5$ ps) used for separate temperature coupling of individual components and C-rescale barostat [53] ($\tau_p = 2.0$ ps). We note that a series of *p*-xylene parameterizations (of different polarity) was employed for the quantitative modelling of *p*-xylene/water interfacial tension (for details see SI).

Table 2. Compositions and initial sizes of two-phase systems, N_i stands for number of molecules.

System	Initial size	$N_{p\text{-xylene}}$	N_{water}	N_{methane}
methane/ <i>p</i> -xylene	4.1×4.1×30.1 nm	500	-	100-2000
methane/water	4.1×4.1×25.1 nm	-	4000	50-1000
<i>p</i> -xylene/water	4.1×4.1×16.1 nm	500	4000	-
<i>p</i> -xylene(methane)/water	4.1×4.1×17.1 nm	500	4000	5-150

Third, to investigate bulk properties, we have carried out bulk simulations (Fig. 3c). This presents an efficient and reliable route for the determination of diffusion, viscosity, density, true Henry's law constant, chemical potentials, or local solution structure. These simulations were performed in isobaric-isothermal (NpT) ensemble with C-rescale barostat ($\tau_p = 2$ ps) and V-rescale thermostat ($\tau_T = 0.5$ ps). Simulation time was 40 ns with the first 20 ns used for equilibration and remaining 20ns used for analysis. The compositions of individual systems are described in Table 3.

Table 3. Compositions and initial sizes of bulk systems, N_i stands for number of molecules.

Component 1	Component 2	N_1	N_2	Molar fraction of the component 2
<i>p</i> -xylene	-	500	-	0
<i>p</i> -xylene	methane	500	5-150	0.01-0.23
<i>p</i> -xylene	water	450-499	1-50	0.002-0.1

water	-	2500	-	0
water	methane	2250-2499	1-250	0.0004-0.1
water	<i>p</i> -xylene	2250-2499	1-250	0.0004-0.1

Theory

Surface tension was calculated from the pressure tensor P_{ij} , which was measured during the slab simulations using the equation

$$\gamma(t) = \frac{L_z}{2} \left(P_{zz}(t) - \frac{P_{xx}(t) + P_{yy}(t)}{2} \right) \quad (7)$$

where L_z is the length of the simulation box along the z -axis, P_{zz} is the perpendicular component (and the macroscopic pressure in the system), while P_{xx} , P_{yy} are the lateral components.

To rationalize changes in surface and interfacial tensions we have determined surface excess of the adsorbing species (Γ_{21}) and connected the micro- and macroscopic views via Gibbs adsorption isotherm, Eq. (8). In this notation, 2 is methane, 1 is *p*-xylene or water, $k_B = R/N_0$ with R being the universal gas constant, T is the thermodynamic temperature, and a_2 and ρ_2 are activity and particle density of methane in the gas phase [54].

$$\left(\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \mu_2} \right) = -\Gamma_{21} \rightarrow \left(\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \rho_2} \right) = -k_B T \frac{\Gamma_{21}}{\rho_2} \left(\frac{\partial \ln a_2}{\partial \ln \rho_2} \right) \quad (8)$$

While Γ_{21} determines the quality and magnitude of surface effect of methane, its activity derivative correction $\left(\frac{\partial \ln a_2}{\partial \ln \rho_2} \right)$, which is strictly positive and usually close to unity, presents a minor (quantitative) effect. Surface excess of methane is evaluated according to Eq. (9) from the equilibrium density profile of methane across the studied interface, where the location of Gibbs dividing surface (z_{GDS}) with respect to the primary solvent is conventionally introduced.

$$\Gamma_{21} = \int_{-\infty}^{z_{GDS}} (\rho_2(z) - \rho_2^{phaseA}) dz + \int_{z_{GDS}}^{+\infty} (\rho_2(z) - \rho_2^{phaseB}) dz \quad (9)$$

Assuming a linear dependence of Γ_{21} on density, $\Gamma_{21} = C\rho_2$, and an ideal behavior of a solute, $\left(\frac{\partial \ln a_2}{\partial \ln \rho_2} \right) = 1$, Eq. (8) allows us to estimate the change in surface tension by $\Delta\gamma = -k_B T \Gamma_{21}$. As a rule of thumb at 298 K, surface excess of one particle per nm^2 equals to a change in surface tension by -4.1 mN/m. The exact application of the protocol is thoroughly demonstrated on methane/water and methane/*p*-xylene system in the SI (Sections SI-2 and SI-3). The results compare quantitatively to surface tensions determined from the pressure tensor. We note that scholar description of a rigorous

accounting for the gas-phase non-ideality into calculation for water-methane system was reported recently [19]. Simulated and experimental surface tension, see Eq. (1) and Eq. (7), are compared in this work to provide MD validation.

The diffusion coefficients were calculated using the mean square displacement according to Einstein's formula (D_{PBC} , Eq. (10), literature [55, 56]). In order to account for long range hydrodynamic effects due to PBC in finite systems, finite size correction was applied and system size independent (true) D_0 evaluated via Eq. (11) as recommended in the literature [57]. In Eq. (11), k_B and T are the Boltzmann constant and thermodynamic temperature, constant $\xi = 2.837297$, η_{MD} is solvent viscosity (either water or *p*-xylene), and L is the side of the cubic simulation box.

As diffusivity is inversely proportional to the viscosity of the solvent medium, another correction [η_{MD}/η_{exp} in Eq. (12)] is routinely applied in the literature [58], accounting for the difference between pure solvent (*p*-xylene/water) viscosity in the simulation (η_{MD}) and in the experiment (η_{exp}). This factor was determined based on experimental and MD viscosity data at 293 K. This uniform scaling proved quantitative for solutions, the viscosity of which does not significantly vary with composition (*e.g.* pure liquids, diluted solutions). However, in the case of complex solutions mixtures of significantly varying density (10-20 mol.% of supercritical methane in liquid *p*-xylene) for which experimental viscosity data are not available, the scaling based on pure liquid viscosities cannot be expected to be quantitative. To practically overcome these various limitations and uncertainties, we have introduced a universal effective scaling parameter [k_η in Eq. (12)] by calibrating diffusion coefficients from MD simulations to our experimental data. To do so, simulated diffusivities are recalculated using Eq. (4) to account for the reference frame introduced in Eq. (3) to account swelling of the macroscopic system. We note that scaling performed in Eq. (12) does not bias temperature or composition dependencies of diffusion coefficients (A, B).

$$D_{PBC} = \frac{1}{6} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} MSD(t) \quad (10)$$

$$D_0 = D_{PBC} + \frac{k_B T \xi}{6 \pi \eta_{MD} L} \quad (11)$$

$$D = D_0 \frac{\eta_{MD}}{\eta_{exp}} k_\eta \quad (12)$$

Solution viscosity is another important property, which steps in the modelling of a diffusion and interpretation of time-resolved neutron images. In this study, we have calculated viscosity via Einstein's approach (-evisco option in gmx energy routine of GROMACS package). To improve convergence, the averaging was performed over 100 independent simulations, each of a length of 2 ns, following the recommendation from the literature.

The volumetric properties, namely partial molar volumes (\bar{V}_i) and volume fractions (ϕ_i), present an important input to continuous modelling, see Eq. (4). Their evaluation from MD simulations starts by a direct calculation of apparent molar volume of methane (V_A^{app}) according to Eq. (13), which requires only system volumes for a series of compositions, *i.e.*, numbers of molecules [$V(N_A, N_B)$] and that of pure *p*-xylene liquid (V_B^*) [59].

$$V_A^{app} = \frac{N_0}{N_A} \left(V(N_B, N_A) - V_B^* N_B \right) \quad (13)$$

Apparent molar volume is available also from NI, see Eq. (6), and thus enables the comparison. Following the formula from the literature [60], partial molar volume of methane (\bar{V}_A) is determined according to Eq. (14)

$$\bar{V}_A = V_A^{app} + x_A x_B \left(\frac{\partial V_A^{app}}{\partial x_A} \right) \quad (14)$$

In case that V_A^{app} is linear in x_A , *i.e.* $V_A^{app} = V_A^\infty + b x_A$, the partial molar volume of methane takes a simple form $\bar{V}_A = V_A^{app} + b x_A x_B = V_A^\infty + b x_A (1 + x_B)$. The calculation of \bar{V}_B is straightforward. The molar fractions and partial molar volume of *p*-xylene are determined from known composition (molar concentrations, c_i) according to:

$$\bar{V}_i = c_i \bar{V}_i \quad (15)$$

Insight into the *p*-xylene-methane and water-methane interactions is captured in the excess (residual) chemical potential μ_A^{ex} . That of methane in the *p*-xylene (or in water) phase was calculated via the Widom test particle insertion method as implemented in GROMACS [61], where ΔE_{12} is the interaction energy of an inserted methane particle and the ensemble average $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is performed over configurations (20 000 frames) of *p*-xylene (or water) phase. 50 000 methane insertions per frame were attempted.

$$\mu_A^{ex} = -k_B T \ln \left\langle e^{\frac{-\Delta E_{12}}{k_B T}} \right\rangle \quad (16)$$

This opens a path for a calculation of the true Henry's law constant (low methane pressure) for methane into pure *p*-xylene (or pure water) of particle density (molar concentration) ρ_B :

$$H^\infty = \rho_B k_B T e^{\frac{\mu_A^{ex}}{k_B T}} \quad (17)$$

thus independently confirming the equilibrium methane concentration in *p*-xylene (or in water), which was determined directly in the slab simulation. The apparent Henry's law constant, determined at finite methane pressures, was calculated from slab simulations according to Eq. (5) and compared to the experimental data calculated using the same equation.

Figure 3. Simulation setups used in this work. The 3-phase slab simulation setup (a), homogeneous liquid phase of *p*-xylene with dissolved methane in contact with water (b), and homogeneous *p*-xylene phase with dissolved methane (c). Methane is as blue spheres, *p*-xylene as green and water as red-white structures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The time-resolved NI observations of the three-phase system from methane, *p*-xylene, and water were used to derive surface tension (γ) for the two phase interfaces, methane diffusivity in the *p*-xylene phase (D_A^B), apparent Henry's law constant for methane in the *p*-xylene phase (H), apparent molar volume of methane in the *p*-xylene phase (V_A^{app}). The so derived experimental data and literature data (see below) were compared to the predictions derived from MD simulations. As three-phase systems of methane, *p*-xylene, and water show very low solubility for the methane–water and *p*-xylene–water pairs, the system can be considered a set of binary systems. Experimental and MD simulation data are listed in Supplementary Information (SI).

The above listed experimentally accessible quantities were insensitive to the *p*-xylene saturation with water (surface tension *p*-xylene/water not considered). Methane diffusivity in the water-saturated *p*-xylene phase (D_A^B) was by $0.8 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$ higher than that for dry *p*-xylene [25] while the average experimental uncertainty was $0.4 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$ being the 95 % confidence interval estimated using the Bonferroni method [33]. Experimental and MD-simulated diffusivities compared well to the ones predicted using the MD simulation once constant k_η in Eq. (12) was optimized (Fig. 4a). Apparent Henry's law constant for methane in *p*-xylene rose, on average, by 5 % due to the saturation of the *p*-xylene phase with water (Fig. 4b), while the average relative experimental uncertainty was 15 %. The respective MD-simulated quantity was overestimated, which originates in the previously reported sensitive propagation of the uncertainty of the excess (residual) chemical potential [21]. Apparent molar volume of methane in *p*-xylene did not change upon the saturation with water to within the experimental

uncertainty of $5 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ (Fig. 4c). Predicted and experimental apparent volume compared well. Predicted surface tension for the methane/*p*-xylene interface overestimated the experimental values having the uncertainty estimated to 2 mN m^{-1} using the Bonferroni method [33], the pressure dependences of both were comparable and could be well parameterized with a semi-empirical model being the product of the simplified Guggenheim's model of temperature dependence [62] and the model of von Szyszkowski [63] of the concentration dependence of surface tension (Fig. 4d).

Figure 4. Experimental and MD-predicted quantities for the system methane (A) and *p*-xylene (B) layered over water (C). Data for water-free systems [25] are marked by *. Methane diffusivity [D_A^B , see Eq. (4), Eq. (12) with $k_\eta = 0.872$] (a), apparent Henry's law constant [H , see Eq. (5)] (b), apparent molar volume of methane [V_A^{app} , see Eq. (6)] (c), and surface tension [γ , see Eq. (1), Eq. (7)] (d) are plotted against methane pressure, temperature is indicated in the legends. In d), AAD is average absolute deviation, regressions of simulated [$T \in (283 \text{ K}, 353 \text{ K})$, $p \in (1 \text{ bar}, 100 \text{ bar})$, $x_A \in (0, 0.23)$] and experimental [$T \in (280.2 \text{ K}, 303.2 \text{ K})$, $p \in (1 \text{ bar}, 100 \text{ bar})$, $x_A \in (0, 0.26)$] data are shown. Literature

data shown in the graphs: # methane and *p*-xylene [22], ## methane and *n*-hexane [64], #\$ methane and benzene [65]. Points are experimental, curves are regressions of simulated data.

Surface tension for methane/*p*-xylene at atmospheric pressure was insensitive to the saturation by water, experimental data (NI) were lower than those from the literature, while prediction overestimated both and captured the expectable dependence on temperature (Fig. 5a). In the case of the *p*-xylene/water interface, surface tension derived as the bulk property using the NI method and Eq. (1), literature data were underestimated and tension decreased with increasing pressure, while data were burdened by the average uncertainty of 16 mN m⁻¹ estimated using the Bonferroni method [33]. High uncertainty is mainly contributed by the low method sensitivity for high $\gamma/\Delta\rho$ that was reported earlier [24]. MD simulation of the *p*-xylene/water interface is an endeavour to which the next section is devoted.

Figure 5. Panel a): Surface tension for the methane (A) and *p*-xylene (B) interface, system layered over water (C). Literature data for water-free systems are marked by * [25], # [66], ## [67], #\$ [68], and #@ [69]. Panel b): Surface tension for the system *p*-xylene (B) and water (C) exposed to indicated pressure of methane (A). Literature *p*-xylene/water systems are marked by & [70] and &# [71].

Comparison of the MD-predictions for the sub-systems with the literature data is of importance particularly in cases in which the NI data are not available. Diffusivity of water in liquid *p*-xylene and methane in liquid water (Fig. 6), along with methane solubility and diffusivity in water (Fig. 7), as well as surface tension and viscosity for pure water (Fig. 8) were predicted and compared to the available experimental data. Although discernible differences of the predictions from the reference datasets were

observed, these comparisons provide assessment of expectable errors, trends and the underlying physics were captured well. Further predictions for the binary systems are summarized in Table 4. For instance, MD enabled the predictions of the diffusivities in the cell reference frame (D_A , D_B), and partial molar volumes of the methane and *p*-xylene (Fig. 9). Such data pertinently complement the observables shown in Fig. 4a, 4c, while they remain hardly accessible experimentally.

Figure 6. Simulated diffusivity of water (C) in infinitely diluted watery solution of *p*-xylene (a), simulated diffusivity of methane (A) in saturated watery solution of methane at 1 bar of methane. Points are simulated (a) and experimental (b), curves indicate regressions of simulated data (see Table 4) and experimental data from the literature: # [72], ## [73].

Figure 7. Methane molar fraction in a saturated solution calculated from the true Henry's law constant (a) and surface tension (b) for methane/water system as a function of methane pressure at 25 °C. Curves are regressions of MD-simulated data, points (#) are from the literature [18].

Figure 8. Surface tension (a) and viscosity (b) of water at saturated vapor pressure. Simulated data are compared to the literature # [36].

Table 4. Simulated partial molar volumes and diffusivities for binaries at the infinite dilution of the indicated component. Data were simulated at 10 and 100 bar, 283, 298, 313, and 353 K, see SI for MD-simulated data. Regressions (p in bar, T in K, \bar{V} in $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$, $D \times 10^9$ in $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, $R = 8.31451 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$ [74]) fit simulated data to within the indicated AAD. A abbreviates methane, B *p*-xylene, C water.

System	Regression	AAD
A (dil.), C	$D_A = 1700 \exp \frac{-17200}{R \cdot T} - 170 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p$	0.15
A (dil.), C	$D_C = 1280 \exp \frac{-15860}{R \cdot T} - 72.8 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p$	0.05
A (dil.), C	$\bar{V}_A = 37.6 + 2.45 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot (T - 298) - 1.43 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot (T - 298)^2 - 1.58 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot p$	0.65
A (dil.), B	$\bar{V}_A = 47.2 + 0.157 \cdot (T - 298) - 695 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot (T - 298)^2 - 6.33 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot p$	0.63

C (dil.), B	$D_C = 930 \exp \frac{-12700}{R \cdot T} - 10.5 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot p$	0.4
C (dil.), B	$D_B = 402 \exp \frac{-12920}{R \cdot T} - 2.140 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot p$	0.04
C (dil.), B	$\bar{V}_C = 21.9 + 51.8 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot (T - 298) - 418 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot (T - 298)^2 + 266 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p$	0.23
B (dil.), C	$D_C = 1280 \exp \frac{-15870}{R \cdot T} - 71 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p$	0.05
B (dil.), C	$D_B = 670 \exp \frac{-1700}{R \cdot T} + 150 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p$	0.05
B (dil.), C	$\bar{V}_B = 117.6 + 0.161 \cdot (T - 298) - 81.3 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot (T - 298)^2 - 4.52 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot p$	0.4

Figure 9. MD simulated diffusivity of methane and *p*-xylene in their binary liquid solution corresponding to the indicated methane pressure [$T \in (283 \text{ K}, 353 \text{ K})$, $p \in (1 \text{ bar}, 100 \text{ bar})$, $x_A \in (0, 0.23)$] with $k_\eta = 0.872$ adjusted based on the comparison of NI and MD simulation. Curves are regressions of simulated data listed in SI.

Microscopic insight into structure of interfaces

Equilibrium MD simulations provide a microscopic view into the studied system. At the mean-field level, equilibrium density distributions of molecules in the bulk phases and at interfaces can be

calculated [75-77]. By performing the simulations of three-phase system, Figure 10 illustrates that the microscopic model captures the *p*-xylene/water interface (see sharp density changes at $z = 0$), low vapor pressure of water, virtually no solubility of methane in water and modest solubility of methane in *p*-xylene. Moreover, the model provides insight to the density distribution (simulation averaged) at the interfaces, from which surface excess or depletion (most importantly of methane) are determined and changes in surface tension evaluated. It is noteworthy that the methane affinity to individual phases differs enough to be directly visualized in the intrinsic simulation snapshot. Top panel of Figure 10 highlights methane molecules in $\Delta z = 5 \text{ \AA}$ slices localized at different phases and interfaces of the system, which is here at equilibrium with methane pressure of 100 bar.

Figure 10. Illustration of the solution structure in the coexisting phases and at the interfaces in system of *p*-xylene, water and methane, $p_{\text{Me}} = 100 \text{ bar}$ and $T = 298 \text{ K}$. The top panel presents a snapshot of the system composition, where water phase (thin red lines representation) in the middle left is in contact with *p*-xylene phase (thin cyan lines) in the middle right, both dense liquid phases are surrounded by methane gas (black spheres). The bottom panel presents the equilibrium density profiles of individual components (see the legend) resolved along the z -axis (perpendicular to the interfaces). Surface enrichment of methane (denoted by peaks) at methane/water and at methane/*p*-xylene interfaces and depletion from the water/*p*-xylene interface (denoted by decrease of density) are clearly visible. These changes in methane density are sufficient to be visually captured by showing methane molecules (cyan, green, yellow, orange, blue, red spheres) at different system locations (slice thickness, $\Delta z = 5 \text{ \AA}$).

The correct behavior of three-phase system model allows us to utilize two-phase systems that are more convenient for quantitative (predictive) modelling of the interface structure and IFT between water and *p*-xylene. Predictions of other quantities were shown above. Figure 11 summarizes the results, both macroscopic and structural properties, determined from MD simulation data. First, the temperature dependence of IFT was directly evaluated from pressure tensor. It is challenging for a simple non-polarizable atomistic *p*-xylene force field (FF) [78] to simultaneously reproduce both correct temperature dependence and correct magnitude of the IFT (≈ 35 mN/m [70, 71]). The left panel of Figure 11 shows that to reproduce the correct magnitude of IFT, reasonable partial charges on the *p*-xylene atoms are required (on the order of $\pm 0.15 e$, from $1.0 \times$ to $0.75 \times$ scaling), however, temperature dependence of IFT is absent in these models. Only when the charges are reduced to ca $0.5 \times$, the temperature dependence of IFT is recovered. To reach the typical experimental slope ≈ 0.1 mN/(m K) [79] partial charges must be reduced by $< 0.25 \times$ scaling, however, these models predict too high absolute magnitude of IFT, which is in the range of ≈ 50 - 60 mN/m (i.e., close to alkane/water IFT [79]). Full details are provided in section SI-1 in the SI.

Next, we analyzed the structure of the *p*-xylene/water interface in the presence of dissolved methane, up to $x_{\text{Me}} = 0.3$ (equivalent to $p_{\text{Me}} = 100$ bar) in the *p*-xylene phase. No significant impact of methane is observed on the structure of *p*-xylene/water interface as documented in Figure S3 in SI. In particular, the width of the interface and the mutual solubility of water and *p*-xylene are unchanged. These results are rather insensitive to the parametrization of the *p*-xylene molecule. By analyzing the density profile of methane at the *p*-xylene/water interface [using Eq. (8) and Eq. (9)], we have found only marginal effect of methane on IFT (< 1 mN/m). This observation is robust with the change of *p*-xylene FF (see Section SI-1). On the qualitative level, however, the choice of *p*-xylene FF qualitatively affects the affinity of methane to the interface, from mild depletion (implying $\Delta\gamma > 0$) to mild enrichment ($\Delta\gamma < 0$) of methane at the interface, for polar and nonpolar model of *p*-xylene respectively (see Figures S3, S4 in SI). This minor affinity of methane contrasts to its surface activity at both surfaces, i.e., methane/water and methane/*p*-xylene, where the changes of IFT are about 5 - $10 \times$ larger (see comparison in the middle panel of Figure 11).

Figure 11. MD simulation prediction of interfacial tension (IFT) of *p*-xylene/water system with changes in temperature (left) or with equilibrium methane gas density (middle). The left panel presents the effect of temperature for *p*-xylene models with full (brown triangles, scaling = 1.0) and reduced partial charges (see the legend for scaling). The middle panel presents estimated changes of IFT ($\Delta\gamma$) with concentration of methane in the gas phase (equivalent to p_{Me}) at 283 K (green) and 353 K (blue). Due to the impact of the *p*-xylene FF (for details see section SI-1), the shaded area reflects the uncertainty in the IFT prediction, nevertheless, $\Delta\gamma$ is small when compared to methane impact on methane/water (black), or methane/*p*-xylene (red) interfaces. The right panel compares the density profiles of methane (black) at methane/*p*-xylene (gas) and methane/*p*-xylene/water interfaces (at 298 K, $p_{\text{Me}} = 100$ bar). The methane densities are aligned in the *p*-xylene phase, which highlight marginal interfacial activity of methane at methane/*p*-xylene/water interface (comparison to the methane/water interface is provided in Fig. S11 in SI).

The surface and interfacial excess of methane are compared in the right panel of Figure 11, where the methane concentration in the *p*-xylene phase is overlaid. A prominent peak in the methane *z*-density profile at methane/*p*-xylene surface is observed and quantified by a substantial surface excess of methane (see also Section SI-3). A similar observation applies for methane/water interface, which results are provided in Figure S11 and in Section SI-2 in SI. In contrast, only minor excess or depletion of methane is found at methane/*p*-xylene/water interface depending on the *p*-xylene FF. This difference in methane affinity may be explained by virtually no solubility of methane in water. In case of *p*-xylene/water interface, water phase presents an inaccessible excluded volume domain for methane, which contrasts with the easily accessible methane gas (fluid) phase. Consequently, the surface excess or depletion of methane at such type of interface (liquid/liquid) as well as the impact on interfacial tension are limited.

CONCLUSIONS

General constraints for interfacial tension (IFT) determination based on the mobile interface shape in wide-bore tubes were analyzed with neutron imaging. The studied three-phase systems were constituted of perdeuterated *p*-xylene ($p\text{-C}_8\text{D}_{10}$) layered over water (10.88 mol.% of H_2O in D_2O), exposed to pressurized methane (CH_4 , 1.0 to 101 bar) at 7.0 to 30.0 °C. This setup enabled to derive the time- and space-resolved evolution of concentration and density of the *p*-xylene phase, and thus enabled to derive the respective surface tensions, diffusivity, solubility, and partial molar volume of methane. While the surface tension for the methane/*p*-xylene interface was determined within $2 \text{ mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$, that for the *p*-xylene/water was burdened with the unacceptable uncertainty of $16 \text{ mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$.

The experimentally accessible quantities (except IFT for *p*-xylene/water due to high uncertainty) and data available from the literature compared well to the predictions of the optimized MD simulation. MD-based predictions of the experimentally inaccessible quantities, namely partial molar volumes and diffusivities, were provided. Moreover, molecular-level analysis focused on the pressurized methane surfactancy showed that the key prerequisite for the surface excess formation is the accessibility of the neighboring phase for the accumulating gas. While methane accumulates at the methane/*p*-xylene and methane/water interfaces to form a thicker layer of adsorbed methane (ca 1.5 nm), a thinner layer of methane (ca 4 Å) is affected to a much smaller extent at the *p*-xylene/water interface. Besides the lack of space for the methane accumulation at the liquid/liquid interface, even minor changes in the parameterization of the charge distribution within the *p*-xylene molecule switches between positive and negative methane accumulation at the *p*-xylene/water interface. While pressurized methane is a surfactant for *p*-xylene and for water, which are model impurities of crude natural gas, it causes minor surfactancy or even increase of IFT for the *p*-xylene/water interface.

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